

RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE IS A GUARANTEE OF INTERETHNIC HARMONY

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Abstract. *The article states that religious tolerance has a content of socio-political and cultural-enlightenment. Also, the basis of freedom of conscience and belief in the New Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept of tolerance in the works of such great scholars as Abdulholiq Gijduvani, Zamakhshari, Marginoni, Moturidi, the importance of religious tolerance during the Timurid era are mentioned.*

Keywords: *tolerance, endurance, Abdulholiq Gijduvani, human tolerance, local tolerance, tolerance between peoples and states UNESCO, New Constitution, Timurids, Enlightenment and religious tolerance.*

Introduction.

In the current process of globalization, the problem of religious tolerance is one of the most urgent issues for the countries of the world community. The Development Strategy of Uzbekistan provides for: “In order to strengthen the environment of interethnic harmony and interreligious tolerance in society: Further improving the system of state support for national cultural centers; Ensuring the consistent implementation of the Concept of State Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of interethnic relations.” The idea of inter-religious tolerance means that people of different religious beliefs live together in one land, one country, on the path of noble ideas and intentions. All religions of the world are based on the idea of virtue, which relies on several virtues such as honesty, peace, kindness and friendship. Also, tolerance encourages people to be honest, clean, kind and humane. Nevertheless, it is necessary to emphasize that today there is no single scientific definition of this concept, which has acquired a deep socio-political and cultural-educational content, but the main qualities and characteristics that it expresses are described in a general way.

Main part.

The word “tolerance” has the same or complementary meaning in almost all languages. Summarizing them, it can be said that “tolerance” has such meanings as patience, endurance, respect for different views and actions, kindness, generosity, forgiveness, compassion.

Tolerance among the peoples of Central Asia and the Middle East: its upbringing has a long history. Our ancestors instilled in their children from a very young age such virtues as patience towards representatives of other religions and nationalities, respect for the culture, language, and customs of other peoples. At the same time, they also promoted the upbringing of tolerance to future generations.

The Sufi scholar Abdulkhalik Gijduvani, considering in his works where tolerance should be manifested, groups it as follows:

Human tolerance - a person's love for all of creation and harmonious behavior.

Family tolerance - openness of the family door and the hearts of family members, hospitality, kindness and care.

Local tolerance - the coexistence and cooperation of relatives, neighbors, representatives of different religions and nationalities, extending a helping hand to each other.

National tolerance - the recognition of each other's customs, beliefs, and ideas, and living together as partners and in harmony.

Tolerance between peoples and states - living in unity and friendship, regardless of nationality, race, gender, status, or place of residence. The adoption of the Declaration of Principles of Tolerance by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) on November 16, 1995 is a vivid proof of this. This declaration also pays attention to freedom of belief and conscience. Article 1 of it defines tolerance as respect for the richness and diversity of the world culture in which we live, the forms and methods of manifestation of human individuality, its acceptance and correct understanding, and freedom of conscience and belief. Our main document states that representatives of all nationalities living in our country, regardless of their nationality, language, belief, social status, constitute the people of Uzbekistan and their rights and interests, as well as freedom of belief, are strengthened. In particular, according to Article 19 of the New Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "All citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the same rights and freedoms and are equal in front of the law, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, belief, personal and social status." Therefore, registration in this way serves as the basis for ensuring the freedom of conscience and belief of people in our country.

Noble qualities of our society, such as mutual respect, kindness and tolerance, the principle of living in harmony with national and universal values, can be seen in the fact that representatives of all nationalities and peoples living in our country are widely recognized by the world community. For this reason, it can be said that the issue of preserving, further developing and enriching the national traditions and values of different nationalities and peoples in our country is under the constant attention of the state policy.

Today, there are more than one hundred and thirty nationalities and ethnic groups in our country, and they live in harmony as children of one family. Therefore, diaspora centers of various nationalities are constantly operating. As a result of the joint, cooperative and harmonious life of such a large number of nationalities and ethnic groups, each of them is becoming spiritually and culturally richer, and under the influence of mutual relations, the lifestyle of our multinational people is further improving. Also, all necessary conditions have been created to ensure their constitutional rights and freedoms and legitimate interests: to get education in their own language, to acquire a profession in accordance with their national values, according to their interests and abilities, and to work. Therefore, ample opportunities have been created for representatives of all nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country to study in their native language. It is worth noting that education is provided in seven languages - Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Kazakh and Tajik in our general secondary schools. Equal conditions have also been created for representatives of all nationalities in higher education institutions, technical schools, vocational schools, academic lyceums, schools and preschool educational institutions. Along with this, the mass media, including newspapers and magazines are published in many languages, and TV and radio broadcasts are clear evidence of the activities of the nationalities living in Uzbekistan in this regard.

Thus, it is worth noting that our country is recognized by the world community as the historical heir of religious tolerance in the true sense of the word. Because the idea of "religious

tolerance" has always been promoted in our country. In particular, it can be noted that the idea of "religious tolerance" in the works of our great scholars such as Zamakhshari, Marginoni, and Moturidi, who came from our land, has been an important factor in ensuring the aspirations of peoples of different faiths living on this land for the well-being of the country. Indeed, Uzbekistan is a tolerant country where people of different nationalities and religious beliefs, regardless of religion, race and nationality, have been living in harmony as one family for centuries, and where people are honored. It is on this land that a large-scale process of mutual enrichment of world cultures has taken place over the centuries. If we look at history, as the Castilian ambassador who was at Timur's court at the beginning of the 15th century testifies, Timur gathered representatives of different religions in Samarkand and did them favor. According to other sources, one of Timur's sons was appointed responsible for meeting the needs of Christians, and he was also responsible for relations with all Christian countries. Therefore, such values in the history of our country are developing in the conditions of the new era. It should be noted that in the current era, Uzbekistan's progressive initiatives to strengthen development, enlightenment and tolerance are recognized by the international community. Just one example: on December 12, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev delivered a speech at the 73rd session of the United Nations General Assembly, and at the proposal of our President, the resolution "Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance" was unanimously adopted by 193 member states of this influential international organization. On July 25, 2023, at the plenary session of the 77th session of the UN General Assembly, the UN adopted a resolution on interfaith tolerance. This resolution was drafted by consensus on the topic "Promoting interfaith and intercultural dialogue and tolerance in the context of combating hate speech". The resolution is adopted every two years, traditionally at the initiative of the Moroccan delegation. The resolution was prepared by 49 states. Uzbekistan is among them. The main purpose and call of the resolution is to condemn acts of violence against religious symbols, sacred books, homes, businesses, property, schools, cultural centers or places of worship, as well as attacks on religious monuments, places of interest and pilgrimage sites in violation of international law.

Conclusions and proposals. In conclusion, for the sake of international harmony, it is very important for every person, community and nation to understand and respect the diversity of cultures that make up humanity. Without tolerance, the foundations of democracy and human rights cannot be strengthened. Just as there is no development and democracy without peace, there is no peace without tolerance.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026" No. PF-60.
2. Collection of "Current Problems of Religious Studies". Publishing and Printing Association "Tashkent Islamic University". Tashkent- 2009.
3. The "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" was adopted at the 28th session of the United Nations Organization (UN) - UNESCO, a specialized agency dealing with issues of education, science and culture, on November 16, 1995
4. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition, which entered into force on May 1, 2023.